

Loading rate controlled stress-driven depolarization of PZT 52/48 and 95/5

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the loading rate dependence of the depolarization of PZT 52/48 and PZT 95/5 is investigated under uniaxial stress at stress rates of 0.1-100 MPa/ms by using a load frame. PZT 52/48 shows a saturation of charge release at ~500 MPa, while PZT 95/5 requires twice the pressure for saturation of depolarization. Depolarization behavior of both types of PZT is dominated by ferroelectric domain switching. Transverse mode experiments indicate that a partial ferroelectric to antiferroelectric phase transformation occurs in PZT 95/5 under uniaxial loading. The results have implications for the design of multifunctional composites intended to take advantage of the ferroelectric to antiferroelectric phase transformation. These results suggest that the stress state must have a large hydrostatic component to fully drive the ferroelectric to antiferroelectric phase transformation.

1 INTRODUCTION

This work is part of a broader program to develop the ability to generate electrical energy from impact and use that energy to modify the response of an active material to shock propagation. The ability to generate an electrical pulse by impacting different compositions of PZT is well understood. One of the largest responses can be obtained by driving a ferroelectric to antiferroelectric phase transformation in PZT 95/5 under uniaxial strain loading using plate impact. Experiments under uniaxial stress loading in split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) [1] indicate a possible rate dependence of domain switching. Little evidence for the ferroelectric to antiferroelectric phase transformation was observed at 1 GPa where it was anticipated. This led to the present set of experiments at lower loading rates. The results indicate that the stress state (uniaxial vs. hydrostatic) and ferroelastic deformation prior to the phase transformation play important roles in mechanical depolarization.

The possibility of rapid depolarization of ferroelectric ceramics driven by shock wave compression was demonstrated by Neilson [2] in 1957. Unlike harvesting energy from oscillatory sources through the piezoelectric response, in the shock environment the maximum energy can be extracted from a single loading cycle at a very high power. This is widely used in pulsed power generation [3]. Previous studies have examined the shock response of ferroelectric ceramic lead zirconate titanate (PZT). Two compositions with a Zr:Ti ratio of 52:48 and 95:5 are of interest due to their proximity to phase boundaries [4], resulting in a small energy barrier between different phases. PZT 52/48 lies on the boundary between a ferroelectric rhombohedral phase and a ferroelectric tetragonal phase. Depolarization can be mechanically driven via non-180° domain switching. PZT 95/5 lies on the boundary between the ferroelectric rhombohedral phase and antiferroelectric orthorhombic phase, and in addition to mechanical depolarization via domain switching, it can also be depoled via a ferroelectric to antiferroelectric phase transformation. This has been achieved under uniaxial strain

shock compression in gas gun experiments. Chhabildas [5] reported that the unpoled PZT 95/5 undergoes a phase transformation at 0.5 GPa and stays in a mixed phase up to 2.6 GPa. Setchell *et al.* expanded the investigation of PZT 95/5 in the shock environment and systematically presented the Hugoniot states, constitutive mechanical properties [6], dielectric properties [7], shock-induced depoling characteristics [8] and the effects of initial porosity and microstructures on the mechanical and electrical behavior [9-11]. Hydrostatic compression has also been used to characterize the ferroelectric material response under quasi-static loading. Valadez *et al.* [12, 13] experimentally investigated the coupled effects of hydrostatic pressure and electric field on the phase transformation in PZT 95/5 and identified the threshold hydrostatic pressure for phase transformation as 330 MPa. The shock behavior of ceramics can also be characterized using SHPB [14, 15]. Dong *et al.* [16] reported that hard PZT4 is significantly rate-sensitive in the stress rate range of 1 MPa/s to 4MPa/ μ s. Khan *et al.* [17] showed some preliminary results of PZT 95/5 under low to mid-strain rate using a load frame, a drop tower and SHPB. Significant temperature and strain rate dependencies were observed.

The depolarization behavior of PZT 52/48 and 95/5 under uniaxial stress at stress rates of 1-100 MPa/ μ s were measured using SHPB [1]. An apparent rate dependence in both types of materials was observed. In this work, the loading rate dependence of PZT 52/48 and 95/5 under uniaxial stress at lower stress rates of 0.1-100 MPa/ms were investigated using a servo-hydraulic load frame. The force history and voltage drop across a current viewing resistor in series with the PZT were recorded using the MTS data acquisition system TestStar, and the stress and released charge density history were calculated based on specimen area measurements.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Bulk PZT 52/48 (TRS 610HD) and 95/5 materials were obtained from TRS Technologies and cut into small thin plate specimens with rectangular shape surfaces by using a diamond dicing saw. Each specimen had a large aspect ratio. Gold electrodes were deposited on the top and bottom surfaces. Prior to the compression tests, each specimen was poled under 2 MV/m at the frequency of 0.2 Hz along the thickness direction. The average remnant polarization was 0.33 C/m² for PZT 52/48 and 0.34 C/m² for PZT 95/5. Each specimen was sandwiched between two polished hardened steel plates with wires connected to the current viewing resistor. Three different resistances were chosen with the larger resistors being used at the lower rates. An alignment fixture [18] and a grease layer were used to obtain a stress state as close as possible to uniaxial. Two 0.12 mm thick Kapton layers were placed between the steel plates and the loading bars for electrical isolation. The material was subjected to a pre-stress of \sim 5 MPa and then loaded at a constant loading rate parallel to the remnant polarization. The stress rate was confirmed using the measured stress history. Additional transverse mode experiments were performed with the remnant polarization perpendicular to the loading direction. All experiments were conducted at ambient temperature (approximately 22°C). A schematic of the load frame and the circuit are shown in Figure 1. Parameters for the experiments are provided in Table 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of load frame compression experiments.

PZT type	Surface area (mm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Loading rate (MPa/ms)	Resistor (kΩ)
52/48	8.94	0.73	0.56	98.9
52/48	11.15	0.73	4.48	98.9
52/48	10.14	0.73	9.86	17.6
52/48	10.20	0.73	49.0	0.98
52/48	10.97	0.73	91.2	0.98
95/5	11.7	0.55	0.43	98.9
95/5	5.16	0.55	1.94	98.9
95/5	6.53	0.55	7.66	98.9
95/5	6.53	0.55	15.3	17.6
95/5	5.58	0.55	89.6	0.98
95/5	11.60/3.7*	0.89	8.62	98.9

*For transverse mode tests, the first surface area is used to calculate the stress and the second is used to calculate the charge density.

Table 1: Dimension of specimens and experimental conditions.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results show similar characteristics. The stress-time curves were linear in the loading regime, indicating a constant loading rate condition. The total released charge was obtained by dividing the voltage by the resistance and then integrating over time. Under uniaxial loading, the poled ferroelectric material undergoes ferroelastic deformation through non-180° domain switching. This process describes the evolution of the ferroelectric domain structures. The associated kinetics include the nucleation of new domains and propagation of domain walls. The domain wall motion occurs in both PZT 52/48 and 95/5 under mechanical loading. Under sufficient stress, PZT 95/5 will undergo a ferroelectric to antiferroelectric phase transformation with a volume reduction. In the loading rates studied the effects of stress waves can be neglected. When the material is fully depoled the released charge density is equivalent to the remnant polarization value.

Figure 2 shows the stress and released surface charge density as a function of time in a typical experiment for both PZT 52/48 (at 0.56 MPa/ms) and 95/5 (at 1.94 MPa/ms). Under constant stress rate loading conditions, both PZT 52/48 and 95/5 show a nonlinear response of released charge. PZT 52/48 fully depoled at a lower stress level (~500 MPa) than PZT 95/5 (~1.1 GPa).

Figure 2: Stress and depolarization history for PZT 52/48 at 0.56 MPa/ms (left) and PZT 95/5 at 1.94 MPa/ms (right).

Figure 3 shows the released charge density as a function of stress for different loading rates for PZT 52/48. Within the experimental detection limits, no significant rate dependence of depolarization on the stress rate was observed in the range of loading rates investigated. Saturation of released charge density is indicated by the slope of the curve approaching zero. All the curves show depolarization saturation at around 500 MPa. The values of the charge density are computed based on the specimen electrode area and the voltage history across the current viewing resistor. The physical area of the specimens, which ideally is identical to the electrode area, were measured using a caliper to within $\pm 25 \mu\text{m}$, introducing 2.5-5% error into the charge density value. However, the electrode area may differ from the specimen area. The gold electrodes were deposited using physical vapor deposition and may not have completely extended to the edges of each specimen.

Figure 3: Depolarization of PZT 52/48: depolarization charge density as a function of stress for various loading rates.

Figure 4 shows the depolarization charge density of PZT 95/5 as a function of stress at different loading rates. Compared to PZT 52/48, twice the stress level ($\sim 1\text{GPa}$) for the saturation of the released charge density is required for PZT 95/5. At high stress levels, the phase transformation can also occur in PZT 95/5. The depolarization behavior in PZT 95/5 may be from a combination of domain switching and phase transformation effects. Transverse loading experiments were performed in an attempt to isolate phase transformation from domain switching behavior.

Figure 5 shows the transverse loading response of PZT 95/5 at 8.62 MPa/ms. The charge density first becomes negative. This indicates that the polarization increases during the initial stage of loading. This is the d_{31} piezoelectric response. As the stress increases, the charge density becomes positive and shows an abrupt jump coincident with a sudden dip in the stress curve. The charge density saturated at about 0.051 C/m^2 . The abrupt jump of the charge density at about 500 MPa is attributed to the onset of the phase transformation. The total released charge density is significantly lower than the remnant polarization. This indicates a possible incomplete phase transformation or a possible short circuit that might be associated with cracking when the specimen undergoes a volume reduction during the phase transformation. These results indicate that the hydrostatic stress driven phase transformation likely plays a role in the depolarization kinetics of PZT 95/5 for the loading rates studied.

Figure 4: Depolarization of PZT 95/5: depolarization charge density as a function of stress for various loading rates.

Figure 5: Stress and depolarization history for PZT 95/5 under the normal mode at 8.62 MPa/ms.

There are multiple potential sources of error in the experiments. In the stress loading rates of 0.1-100 MPa/ms, neither PZT 52/48 nor PZT 95/5 exhibited a strong rate dependence of depolarization. Domain switching dominates the material response up to 1 GPa for both materials. As the axial stresses within the specimen and platen increase, the mismatch in lateral expansion of the two materials causes the specimen to be placed in a state of lateral compressive stress. Grease was used between the specimen and the platens to reduce this effect. The phase transformation induces a volumetric contraction. This potentially leads to a tensile stress in the specimen due to constrain by the platens during the phase transformation. Stress concentrations can occur when the surfaces of the specimen and platen are not highly parallel, or due to a slight bending effect of the platens around the

edges of the specimen. Even with these precautions, the tensile stress introduced by lateral confinement, and the stress concentrations introduced due to uneven surfaces and bending effect around the edges of the specimen, may not have been completely mitigated. Catastrophic failure can be seen within the stress history as a deviation from linear loading. Smaller failure events, which are not evident in the stress history, can be inferred from spikes in the voltage history of the current viewing resistor. The presented results were taken from specimens that did not show evidence of failure within the stress or voltage history prior to depolarization saturation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The stress loading rate dependence of depolarization for PZT 52/48 and PZT 95/5 was investigated in the loading range of 0.1-100 MPa/ms, with a maximum stress up to 1 GPa for PZT 52/48 and 1.4 GPa for PZT 95/5 by using a load frame. Neither PZT 52/48 nor PZT 95/5 exhibited a strong rate dependence of depolarization in the range studied. The released charge density of PZT 52/48 saturated at ~500 GPa, while PZT 95/5 required twice the pressure for the saturation of polarization. Since the saturated charge density for both types of PZT is lower than their remnant polarization value, the materials may not have been fully depoled. Depolarization behavior of both types of PZT is dominated by domain switching. The transverse loading experiments indicated that the phase transformation likely contributed to the depolarization response of PZT 95/5.

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